

Exploring the Antimicrobial Properties of *Dicentra scandens*: A Promising Natural Agent

Sunita Rana*, Rohan Kumar

Department of Biological Sciences, Assam University, Silchar, 788011, Assam, India; Department of Microbiology, University of North Bengal, Darjeeling, 734013, West Bengal, India

Citation: Sunita Rana*, Rohan Kumar (2025). Exploring the Antimicrobial Properties of *Dicentra scandens*: A Promising Natural Agent. *Psychiatry*, 17(12), 65-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19096769>

ABSTRACT

Dicentra scandens (D. Don) Walp. locally called as 'Jogi Lahara' belongs to the Family *Fumariaceae* and is used in traditional medicine in Sikkim, a North Eastern state of India. The present study investigated the antimicrobial properties of aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. against some test Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria. Using agar well diffusion method, aqueous and methanol extracts of roots of *Dicentra scandens* were tested against *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 1089), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MTCC 3384), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 1034), *Proteus vulgaris* (MTCC 742), *Salmonella typhi* (MTCC 733), *Shigella flexneri* (MTCC 1457), *Vibrio cholerae* O139(MTCC 3906), *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC 6840) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 7443). Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) were also evaluated. Promising antimicrobial activity was exhibited by methanol extract of *Dicentra scandens*. The methanol extract was further characterized by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. The GC-MS analysis revealed 29 compounds and the major compounds detected were Protopine (53.78%) and Corydine (18.20%). Thus, the alkaloids are predominant phytoconstituents of the extract and could be attributed to its antimicrobial activity. The results of the present study indicate that, *Dicentra scandens* can be a source of potential antimicrobial agent and can be explored further for its therapeutic use.

Keywords: Alkaloid, Antimicrobial, Corydine, *Dicentra scandens*, GC-MS analysis, Protopine

INTRODUCTION

Dicentra scandens (D. Don) Walp. is a climbing perennial herb with tuberous rootstock¹, belonging to the family *Fumariaceae*. It is distributed in temperate Northern Asia and North America¹. Various tribal communities of Nepal and North East India traditionally use *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. as an important ethnomedicinal plant². The herbalist from Nagaland use this plant for the treatment of malaria, typhoid, viral fever, diabetes, pneumonia, high blood pressure, diarrhoea, dysentery, flatulence, cut or injury³. Crushed tuberous root with water is taken against fever, stomach ache and high blood pressure in Manipur⁴. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of n-hexane, ethyl acetate and ethanolic extracts of root of *Dicentra scandens* against potential wound pathogens has been investigated⁵. The root juice of *Dicentra scandens* is useful in gastritis. Leaf paste or juice is applied on cuts and wounds⁶. Dried root powder of *Dicentra scandens* is administered orally during gastritis by the Limboo tribe residing in South-West Khangchendzonga biosphere reserve in West Sikkim, India⁷. Ecologically, Yonzon, et al. (2012) categorised *Dicentra scandens* as a rare medicinal herb found in Darjeeling Himalaya of West Bengal, India⁸. The present study aims to document and investigate the antimicrobial property of *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. collected from Damthang, South district of Sikkim, India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

All the chemicals and reagents used including solvents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, USA, Merck, Germany and HiMedia, India and were of analytical grade. **Collection and identification of plant sample** Tuberous roots of *Dicentra scandens* were collected from Damthang (27°13'60" N) South District of Sikkim (India). A voucher specimen (Accession number 09734) was deposited at the herbarium of the Taxonomy Division, Department of Botany, University of North Bengal, India. **Preparation of crude methanol and aqueous extracts** The root of *Dicentra scandens* were cut in small pieces and dried in shade. The dried plant material was ground into powder using Waring blender (Cole Parmer, RZ-0424521). The powdered material 20grams each was extracted with 200ml of respective solvents (aqueous and methanol) for 24 hours using orbital shaker. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure in a Rotary evaporator (Buchi, Switzerland, R-3). The concentrated extract was stored at 4°C till further analysis⁹. Prior to antibacterial assay, extracts were dissolved in 0.25% dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO). **Phytochemical analysis** Aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* were subjected to qualitative phytochemical analyses to examine the phytoconstituents namely phenol, flavonoid, tannin, saponin, steroid, anthocyanin, alkaloid, glycoside, carbohydrate, protein and fat^{10,11,12,13}.

Figure 1: A. *Dicentra scandens* (D.Don) Walp. B. Tuberous root C. Dried sample from tuberous root D. Powdered sample.

Figure 2: Zone of inhibition against different test microorganisms by aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* at the concentration of 25mg/ml.

The data represents mean ± SD. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

Table 1: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, Minimum Bactericidal Concentration in mg/ml and MIC index of the extracts against test bacterial strains.

		Aqueous extract	Methanol extract
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	MIC	-	25

	MBC	-	50
	MIC Index	-	2
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	MIC	-	100
	MBC	-	100
	MIC Index	-	1
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	MIC	-	100
	MBC	-	100
	MIC Index	-	1
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	MIC	50	50
	MBC	200	100
	MIC Index	4	2
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	MIC	-	25
	MBC	-	100
	MIC Index	-	4
<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	MIC	-	12.5
	MBC	-	50
	MIC Index	-	4
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O139	MIC	-	6.25
	MBC	-	6.25
	MIC Index	-	1
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	MIC	-	100
	MBC	-	200
	MIC Index	-	2
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	MIC	100	25
	MBC	200	100
	MIC Index	2	4

‘-’absence of zone of inhibition in agar well diffusion method at higher concentration (400mg/ml).

Figure 3: Zone of inhibition against different test microorganisms by aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* at the concentration of 50mg/ml.

The data represents mean ± SD. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

Figure 4: Zone of inhibition against different test microorganisms by aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* at the concentration of 100mg/ml.

The data represents mean ± SD. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

Figure 5: Zone of inhibition against different test microorganisms by aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* at the concentration of 200mg/ml.

The data represents mean ± SD. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

Determination of total phenolic content

Total phenolic content was determined according to FolinCiocalteu method¹⁴ using gallic acid as the standard. Total phenolic content was represented as mg of gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per gram of extract. The entire test was done in triplicate and their mean value was represented.

Determination of total flavonoid content The total flavonoid content was estimated by aluminium chloride colorimetric method¹⁵ using rutin as a standard reference. Total flavonoid content was expressed as mg of rutin equivalent (RE) per gram of extract. The entire test

Table 2: Total phenolic, flavonoid and tannin content of aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens*.

Extracts of <i>Dicentra scandens</i>	Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g) \pm SD	Total flavonoid content (mg RE/g) \pm SD	Total tannin content (mg TAE/g) \pm SD
Methanol extract	12.405 \pm 0.037	2.366 \pm 0.057	23.920 \pm 0.036
Aqueous extract	5.052 \pm 0.200	3.166 \pm 0.246	19.240 \pm 0.017

Each value is expressed as mean \pm SD. GAE; gallic acid equivalent, RE; rutin equivalent, TAE; tannic acid equivalent. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

Figure 6: Zone of inhibition against different test microorganisms by aqueous and methanol extracts of *Dicentra scandens* at the concentration of 400mg/ml.

*Methanol vs. Aqueous ($P < 0.05$). The data represents mean \pm SD. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

was done in triplicate and their mean value was represented.

Determination of total tannin content Total tannin content was determined by Folin Denis spectrophotometric method using tannic acid as reference standard¹⁶. Total tannin content was expressed as mg of tannic acid equivalent (TAE) per gram of extract. The entire test was done in triplicate and their mean value was represented.

Determination of antimicrobial activity The antimicrobial assay was performed by following standard agar well diffusion method¹⁷. The test bacteria used in this study including *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 1089), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MTCC-3384),

Pseudomonas aeruginosa (MTCC-1034), *Proteus vulgaris* (MTCC-742), *Salmonella typhi* (MTCC 733), *Shigella flexneri* (MTCC 1457), *Vibrio cholerae* O139 (MTCC 3906), *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC- 6840) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC-7443) were obtained from Microbial Type Culture Collection and Gene Bank (MTCC), Institute of Microbial Technology (IMTECH), Chandigarh, India. The test plant extracts were dissolved in 0.25% dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) to final stock concentrations of

400mg/ml and sterilized by filtration through 0.45 μ m cellulose acetate membrane filters (Sartorius). Various concentrations (25mg/ml, 50mg/ml, 100mg/ml, 200mg/ml, 400mg/ml) of aqueous and methanol extracts were prepared using stock concentration. DMSO (0.25%) was used as the negative control. Gentamicin (0.1mg/ml)¹⁸ was used as the positive control. Antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the diameter of inhibition zone (DIZ)¹⁹ inclusive of well diameter of 8mm. All the tests were performed in triplicate. The extracts with antibacterial activity were serially diluted for concentrations ranging from 400–0.048 mg/ml for determination of their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) according to the method of Wiegand et al. (2008)²⁰. Minimum bactericidal concentration was determined according to the method described by Heredia et al. (2005)²¹.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry analysis The extract which showed maximum antimicrobial activity, specifically methanol extract, was subjected to GC-MS analysis on a GCMS- QP210 Plus system (Shimadzu), at the Advanced Instrumentation Research Facility (AIRF), Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India. In case of

GC-MS analysis the interpretation for the mass spectrum analysis was done using the database of the National Institute of Standard Technology (NIST11)

(Figure 2). At the concentration of 50mg/ml, the extract exhibited antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio cholerae* and

Figure 7: Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry chromatogram of methanol extract of *Dicentra scandens*.

library and WILEY8 library as provided by the Advanced Instrumentation Research Facility (AIRF), Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism V5.01 (San Diego, USA). The data were analysed using Two-Way ANOVA. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study investigated the antimicrobial activity of *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. collected from Damthang, South district of Sikkim, India. Antimicrobial activity of aqueous and methanol extracts of roots of *Dicentra scandens* was evaluated against nine test microorganisms namely *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Vibrio cholerae* O139, *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The methanol extract exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher antimicrobial activity as compared to the aqueous extract. The methanol extract was found to be effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* at the concentration of 25mg/ml which was the lowest concentration used for antimicrobial assay in our study

(Figure 3). At the concentrations of 100mg/ml and 200mg/ml, the methanol extract inhibited the growth of most of the test microorganisms except *Shigella flexneri* (Figure 4 and Figure 5). However, at the concentration of 400mg/ml the methanol extract exhibited antimicrobial activity against all the nine test microorganisms with the largest zone of inhibition (26 mm) observed in *Staphylococcus aureus* (Figure 6). On the other hand, at the concentration of 400mg/ml the aqueous extract inhibited the growth of two test microorganisms namely *Proteus vulgaris* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Figure 6). It is interesting to note that the zone of inhibition (17.33 ± 0.57 mm) formed by aqueous extracts against *Proteus vulgaris* was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than that of the methanol extract (Figure 6). At a concentration of 200mg/ml the aqueous extract inhibited the growth of only *Proteus vulgaris* (Figure 5). For aqueous extract the MIC values were comparatively higher with 50mg/ml for *Proteus vulgaris* and 100mg/ml for *Staphylococcus aureus*. The MBC value was 200mg/ml for both the test microorganisms. In case of methanol extract the MIC and MBC values ranged from 6.25mg/ml to 100mg/ml and 6.25mg/ml to 200mg/ml respectively (Table 1). Based on the MIC index value which was ≤ 4 ,

both the extracts were found to be bactericidal in nature. The value of MIC index determines whether the plant extract is bactericidal or bacteriostatic in nature. When the MIC index is ≤ 4 , the extract is bactericidal and when the MIC index is >4 , the extract is bacteriostatic²².

The qualitative phytochemical analysis of the aqueous and methanol extracts revealed the presence of flavonoid, anthocyanin, phenol, tannin, alkaloid, steroid and

Table 3: Components (more than 1 % peak area) detected by GC-MS a

Sl. No.	Retention Time	% Area	Compound Name	Formula	M
1	5.196	1.13	2,3-Dihydro-3,5-Dihydroxy-6-Methyl-4H-Pyran-4-One	C ₆ H ₈ O ₄	144
2	11.442	1.09	1,3,4,5-Tetrahydroxy-acid	C ₇ H ₁₂ O ₆	192
3	15.064	1.34	Pentadecanoic acid	C ₁₅ H ₃₀ O ₂	
4	16.761	1.99	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	
5	16.802	3.27	cis-Vaccenic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	
6	24.626	1.51	Hordenine	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ NO	165
7	26.668	18.20	Corydine	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ NO ₄	341
8	29.567	53.78	Protopine	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ NO ₅	353

glycoside. Saponin was detected only in the aqueous extract. In the quantitative analysis, the methanol extract was found to contain comparatively higher amount of total tannin content (23.920 ± 0.036 mg TAE/g) (Table 2). Presence of high amount of tannin may have contributed

extract m
activity
methano
efficienc
Figure 7

A

Figure 8: Chemical structure of the major alkaloids in methanol extract

to the antimicrobial activity of the methanol extract of *Dicentra scandens*. Tannin exerts its antimicrobial effects by inhibition of extracellular microbial enzymes, by interfering with the substrates required for microbial growth or direct action on microbial metabolism through inhibition of oxidative phosphorylation²³. Similarly, the highest phenolic content (12.405 ± 0.037 mg GAE/g) was observed in the methanol extract (Table 2). Hence the presence of high amount of phenolic compounds in

combination with other phytochemicals in the methanol extract of *Dicentra scandens*. The GC-MS analysis revealed twenty nine compounds. The major compounds detected were Protopine (53.78%) and Corydine (18.20%) (Table 3). Both the compounds detected were alkaloids and possess various biological activities (Table 3). Alkaloids are the nitrogenous compound which interferes with cell division thereby exerting antimicrobial effect²⁵. Protopine has been reported to have antibacterial activity²⁶. Similarly, Corydine has DNA damaging activity²⁷. Nakhuru et al. (2013) reported that alkaloid extract from the root of *Dicentra scandens* exhibited antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus mycoides*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterobacter cloacae* and some fungal strains²⁸. In the present study, the methanol extract of *Dicentra scandens* (D.Don) Walp. showed antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Vibrio cholerae* O139, *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus* which are associated with various human diseases. The antimicrobial activity in the extract may be related to the presence of high amount of alkaloid along with phenolic compounds in the extract. However, further investigations are required to isolate and characterise the various bioactive components of *Dicentra scandens* responsible for the antimicrobial activity.

CONCLUSION

In this study the methanol extract of the root of *Dicentra scandens* exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative test bacteria. The antimicrobial activity of the extract could be due to the presence of the high amount of alkaloids in the extract as detected by the GC-MS analysis. The results of the present study revealed potential antimicrobial activity of *Dicentra scandens* (D.Don) Walp. against the test Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria and thus may provide a scientific rationale for the use of *Dicentra scandens* (D.Don) Walp. in traditional medicine. Hence the root of this plant could be a potential source of natural antimicrobial agent.

REFERENCES

1. The Wealth of India (A Dictionary of Indian Raw Materials and Industrial Products). Raw materials, 1952; vol.III: D-E (with index to volumes I-III), CSIR, New Delhi, 53-54.
2. Pfoze NL, Kumar Y, Myrboh B. Phytochemical screening to validate the ethnomedicinal uses of *Dicentra scandens* (D.Don) Walp. leaf and root tuber. *Journal of Non-Timber Forest Product* 2010; 17(3): 335-338.
3. Pfoze NL, Chiezou DN. *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. A highly potent ethnomedicinal plant against malaria, high blood pressure and diabetes. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* 2006; 52:268-70.
4. Pfoze NL, Kumar Y, Myrboh B. Screening of bioactive phytochemicals obtained from lesser known ethnomedicinal plants of Senapati district of Manipur, India. *Pleione* 2013; 7(2): 489-50.
5. Nakhuru KS, Pfoze NL, Gogoi J, Chattopadaya P, Veer V. *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. root phytochemical constituents against potential wound pathogens. *American Journal of Phytomedicine and Clinical Therapeutics* 2014; 2(7): 815-822.
6. Sharma TP, Sharma S. Enumeration of species, in: *Medicinal Plants of Sikkim*, first ed. Beracah Printing and Stationary, Gangtok, 2010; 85.
7. Badola HK, Pradhan BK. Plants used in healthcare practices by Limboo tribe in South – West of Khangchendzonga Biosphere Reserve, Sikkim, India. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* 2013; 12(3):355-369.
8. Yonzon R, Bhujel RB, Rai S. Genetic resources, current ecological status and altitude wise distribution of medicinal plants diversity of Darjeeling Himalaya of West Bengal, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine* 2012; 2(1):S439-S445.
9. Bissa S, Bohra A. Antibacterial potential of pot Marigold. *Journal of Microbiology and Antimicrobials* 2011; 3:51-54.
10. De S, Dey N, Ghosh AK. Phytochemical investigation and chromatographic evaluation of the different extracts of tuber of *Amorphaphallus paeonifolius* (Araceae). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research* 2010; 1:150-157.
11. Sofowora A. Screening plants for bioactive agents. In: *Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medicine in Africa*, Nigeria: Spectrum Books Ltd; Sunshine House, Ibadan, 1993; 134-156.
12. Tiwari P, Kumar B, Kaur M, Kaur G, Kaur H. Phytochemical screening and extraction: a review. *Internationale Pharmaceutica Scientia* 2011; 1:98-106.
13. Tresa GE, Evans WC. Pharmacological activities of natural Products, general methods associated with the phytochemical investigation of herbal products. In: *Parmacognosy*. Saunders Publisher, London, 2009; 135-147.
14. Slinkard K, Singleton VL. Total phenol analyses: automation and comparison with manual methods. *American Journal of Enology and Viticulture* 1977; 28:49-55.
15. Chang C, Yang M, Wen H, Chern J. Estimation of total flavonoid content in *Propolis* by two complementary colorimetric methods. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis* 2002; 5:78-82.
16. Singh R, Verma PK, Singh G. Total phenolic, flavonoids and tannin contents in different extracts of

- Artemisia absinthium*. Journal of Intercultural Ethnopharmacology 2012; 1:101-104.
17. National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards: Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. In: Ninth Informational Supplement, NCCLS 1999; 19: 21.
18. Shihabudeen MS, Priscilla H, Kavitha T. Antimicrobial activity and phytochemical analysis of selected Indian folk medicinal plants. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research 2010; 1:430434.
19. Perez C, Paul M, Bazerque P. An antibiotic assay by the agar well diffusion method Acta Biologica et Medicine Experimentalis 1990; 15:113-115.
20. Wiegand I, Hilpert K, Hancock REW. Agar and broth dilution methods to determine the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of antimicrobial substances. Nature Protocol 2008; 3:163-175.
21. Heredia N, Escobar M, Rodriguez C, Garcia S. Extracts of *Haematoxylon brasiletto* inhibit growth, verotoxin production, and adhesion of enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* O157:H7 to HeLa cells. Journal of Food Protection 2005; 68:1346-1351.
22. Kone WM, Kamanzi Atindehou K, Kacou-N'Douba A, Dosso M. Evaluation of 17 medicinal plants from Northern Cote d'Ivoire for their *In vitro* activity against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines 2007; 4:17-22.
23. Scalbert A. Antimicrobial properties of tannins. Phytochemistry 1991; 30(12): 3875-3883.
24. Sultana B, Anwar F, Ashraf M. Effect of extraction solvent/ technique on the antioxidant activity of selected medicinal plant extracts. Molecules 2009; 14:2167-2180.
25. Olaleye MT. Cytotoxicity and antibacterial activity of methanolic extract of *Hibiscus sadariffa*. Journal of Medicinal Plants Research 2007; 1:009-013.
26. Vacek J, Walterova D, Vrubleova E, Simanek V. The chemical and biological properties of protopine and allocryptopine. Heterocycles 2010; 81(8):1773-1789.
27. Goren AC, Zhou BN, Kingston DG. Cytotoxic and DNA damaging activity of some aporphine alkaloids from *Stephania dinklagei*. Planta Medica 2003; 69(09): 867-868.
28. Nakhuru KS, Pfoze NL, Goswami S, Gogoi HK. Investigation of the antimicrobial activity of crude alkaloid extract of *Dicentra scandens* (D. Don) Walp. tuberous root. Journal of Experimental Biology and Agriculture Sciences 2013; 1:102-105.
29. Mohanambal R, Murugaiah K. GC-MS determination of bioactive constituents of *Furcraea foetida* leaf. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research 2015; 4(10):1160-1166.
30. Kumar S, Sivakumar T, Kt A, Mythili N. GC-MS evaluation of bioactive phytochemicals of commercial green teas (*Camellia sinensis*) of India. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research 2015; 8(3):278-282.
31. Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Databases; [cited 2016 September 3]. Available from: <http://www.ars-grin.gov/duke/>.
32. Kumar S, Samyurai R, Nagarajan N. Gas chromatography and mass spectrometry analysis of bioactive constituents of *Adiantum Capillus-Veneris* L. International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 2014; 6:60-63.
33. Schweitzer A, Wright S. Action of hordenine compounds on the central nervous system. The Journal of Physiology 1938; 92(4):422.